

SECURITY MARKET OVERVIEW: TRENDS & INSIGHTS FROM THE SICUR EXHIBITION

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About ENACT

ENACT is a knowledge network focused on the fight against crime and terrorism (FCT). The network is funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme in Cluster 3 – Civil Security for Society. The project addresses the call topic HORIZON-CL3-2022-SSRI-01-02 ‘Knowledge Networks for Security Research & Innovation’, aiming to collect, aggregate, process, disseminate and make the most of the existing knowledge in the FCT area.

The project aims to satisfy two major ambitions,

- Provide evidence-based support to the decision-makers in the EU research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem in the FCT domain, targeted explicitly at enabling more effective and efficient programming of EU-funded R&I for the fight against crime and terrorism.
- Act as a catalyst for the uptake of innovation by enhancing the visibility and reliability of innovative FCT security solutions.

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Acronyms

AR	Analytical Report
CBRN	Chemical, Biological, Radiological, Nuclear
CCTV	Closed-Circuit Television
CDTI	Centro para el Desarrollo Tecnológico y la Innovación
CERIS	Community of European R&I for Security
EU	European Union
FCT	Fight against Crime and Terrorism
INTA	Instituto Nacional de Técnica Aeroespacial
LEA	Law Enforcement Agency
PPE	Personal Protection Equipment
R&I	Research and Innovation
SICUR	Salón Internacional de la Seguridad
WP	Work Package

What is SICUR?

SICUR [1] is the international reference fair in Spain for Security. Every two years, it brings together companies, associations, professionals and users of global security in the public and private spheres in Madrid.

Innovation and technological development are the main protagonists of this professional meeting that addresses comprehensive security from five areas: security, cybersecurity, fire and emergency safety, occupational safety and health at work. SICUR's agenda is firmly rooted in the advancement of societal well-being and developmental progress, serving as a catalyst for the exchange of knowledge and the proliferation of cutting-edge technologies.

Particularly pertinent to the Fight against Crime and Terrorism (FCT), SICUR illuminates the forefront of security innovation with a focus on two main domains:

- **Security:** solutions dedicated to electronic security, physical security and security services. All technological innovations are at the service of the protection of property and lives, such as intelligent access control and alarm systems, video surveillance technologies, perimeter protection solutions, intrusion detection systems, integrated security systems and equipment for security forces and bodies.
- **Cybersecurity:** portfolio of robust solutions and tools for the protection of company information, systems and data against the spectrum of cyber threats. This event empowers participants with critical insights into the cyber threat landscape, enhancing their ability to navigate and counteract potential cyber-attacks with precision and foresight. Attendees are introduced to cutting-edge security technologies that ensure the protection of critical digital assets. This includes securing data across electronic systems, computers, mobile phones, servers, and networks, safeguarding against unauthorized access and ensuring the integrity and confidentiality of digital information. The event highlights responsive measures and recovery techniques to mitigate the impact of security breaches.

[1] SICUR event website: <https://www.ifema.es/sicur>

A view on the Security Market

Bringing together over 46 000 security professionals, from 80 countries, around 650 exhibitors, SICUR can be taken as a benchmark of the latest tendencies within the Security Market. The diversity and innovation showcased by exhibitors, coupled with the thematic focus of the conferences over the event's four days, reflect the current pulse and direction of the security sector. This report systematically aligns exhibitor profiles and conference themes with the EU Security Market Taxonomy [2], in order to obtain a quantitative and comparable assessment that can serve as a reference for guiding future R&I programming.

Exhibitors

SICUR counted on 654 exhibitors [3] showing a comprehensive display of the latest in security equipment and technology. The spectrum of areas addressed includes intrusion security, fire prevention, occupational health, traffic protection, cybersecurity, defence, and insights from the technical press and associations, illustrating the event's broad coverage of security concerns.

Notably, applications such as **intrusion security, traffic protection, cybersecurity** and **defence** stand out for their relevance to the FCT domain, although their applicability assumes great interest in other domains, such as search and rescue or military applications. A meticulous analysis of SICUR's exhibitor portfolio under these categories revealed a total of 113 exhibiting companies with offerings considered relevant for the FCT domain. The exhibition also featured a large exhibition space dedicated to Spanish police forces, including the Guardia Civil, Policia Nacional, and regional police forces such as Ertzaintza (Basque Country), Mossos d'Esquadra (Catalonia), among others.

As depicted in Figures 1 and 2, the exhibiting private companies (technology providers) have been mapped according to the EU Security Market taxonomy in the Functions and Technology domains. This classification aids in discerning how the market's offerings at SICUR align with or diverge from established R&I priorities and trends, providing valuable insights for strategic planning and development within the security sector (see Appendix A for more information).

[2] European Commission - EU security market study. Available at: https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/ceris-community-european-research-and-innovation-security/eu-security-market-study_en

[3] SICUR exhibitors: <https://www.ifema.es/en/sicur/exhibitors/catalogue>

Regarding the coverage of FCT functions (see Figure 1), the number of exhibitors addressing **Physical access control** and **Monitoring and Surveillance** functions is significantly higher. It is also worth mentioning the high number of exhibitors addressing **Personal and other equipment**. According to the ENACT Analytical Report on EU FCT R&I priorities 2014-2024 (ENACT AR #1) [4], which reviews a total of 76 topics (including subtopics) published by the Commission in the FCT domain, the functions of Physical access control, Monitoring and Surveillance and Personal and other equipment appear in the 11th, 7th and 9th respectively. This shows a relative shift in focus between the market offer at SICUR and the R&I priorities addressed at the EU-funded R&I programme.

FCT Functions

Figure 1 – Mapping of the exhibiting private companies in the Functions domain, according to the EU Security Market taxonomy.

[4] ENACT Analytical Report #1“FCT R&I: AN ANALYSIS OF EU PRIORITIES 2014- 2024”: <https://enact-eu.net/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/ENACT-Analytical-Report-01-FCT-RI-An-analysis-of-EU-priorities-2014-2024.pdf>

In the technology domain (see Figure 2), and in correlation with the Functions analysis above, **Access control/authorisation systems** and **Surveillance systems** were the most present at the exhibition. In particular, video surveillance systems (CCTV systems, cameras and sensors, video analytics) were probably the biggest offer at the exhibition. In this technology, it was very frequent to see exhibitor stands of companies who distributed and integrated products from third-country providers (non-EU, notably China and US). Under the Surveillance systems category, there was also a significant presence of small tactical drones and autonomous ground vehicles. Under the Access control category, the exhibitors showcased mainly control gates, biometric identification/authentication, smart locks, etc. **PPE and safety equipment** were also among the most showcased products, including personal protective equipment, uniforms and shoes and other ancillary items which are commonly used by law enforcement.

Technology

Figure 2 – Mapping of the exhibiting private companies in the Technology domain, according to the EU Security Market taxonomy.

Themes of interest

Conferences

During the four days of the exhibition, a number of conferences [5] were held, addressing topics that provide valuable insights into the current pulse of the security market, revealing areas of apparent heightened interest and capturing the attention of both demand and supply sides of the market.

The list of conferences relevant to FCT have been reviewed and mapped to the policy and functions taxonomy (available in Appendix B). In this case, the technology component has not been mapped as the conferences rarely addressed one technology in particular, even if in some cases noting the policy area or the function addressed an easy correlation could be done with some key technologies.

Figures 3 and 4 show a summary of the analysis carried out on the SICUR conferences. This analysis shows that, even if cybersecurity was not a main element of the exhibition, it was however widely addressed at the conferences, showing the high interest of the security community in the protection of information systems.

The high interest shown during these conferences for protection against CBRN incidents and for personal and other equipment also indicates the importance given by the community for the safety and protection of LEA first responders.

[5] SICUR conferences: <https://www.ifema.es/sicur/horario-actividades>

Figure 3 - Mapping of the SICUR conferences in the Policy domain, according to the EU Security Market taxonomy.

FCT Functions

Figure 4 - Mapping of the SICUR conferences in the Functions domain, according to the EU Security Market taxonomy.

Innovation

Innovation was explicitly addressed at SICUR, which also serves as a proxy measure of the themes of interest for the security community. On one hand, a conference was organized on February 27, jointly between CDTI INNOVACIÓN, INTA and FUNDACIÓN MADRI+D, which included 3 consecutive events:

- “Flash” Horizon Europe Cluster 3 information day during the morning of the 27th – approximate attendance: 140 people.
- Pitch presentations and brokerage with special participation of a delegation from Turkey: about 120 people attended, 10 quick presentations were made, taking into account that the Turkish delegation was about 20 people.
- CERIS events on high-impact, low-probability catastrophes, which took place during the afternoon of February 27. Approximate participation: 70 people.

Innovation was also present at the exhibition, with the showcase of the 26 most cutting-edge products brought by the exhibitors in the so-called “Innovation Gallery” [6]. Following the review of these 26 products, 7 have been found which are relevant for the FCT domain (see Appendix C). These include mainly advanced surveillance systems, secure communication devices and screening devices. In the majority of them, Artificial Intelligence was highlighted by the vendor as a key enabling technology for an increased performance.

SICUR reference information

Name of the event: Salón Internacional de la Seguridad SICUR

Dates: 27 February – 1 March 2024

Location: IFEMA, Avda. del Partenón, 5, 28042 Madrid, Spain

Website: <https://www.ifema.es/sicur>

Relevant news:

- <https://www.ifema.es/sicur/noticias/sicur-2024-balance>
- <https://een-madrid.es/event/brokerage-event-feria-internacional-cluster-3-civil-security-for-society/>
- <https://infodefensatv.infodefensa.com/videos/view/6832634/sicur-2024-feria-internacional-seguridad-madrid>
- <https://www.rtve.es/play/videos/telediario-1/sicur-feria-referencia-del-sector-seguridad-reune-madrid-mas-1350-empresas/3497701/>

[6] SICUR Innovation Gallery products: <https://www.ifema.es/sicur/galeria-innovacion>

APPENDIX A - SICUR Exhibitors

The following table shows the SICUR exhibitors that are relevant to the FCT domain and which have been used in the analysis presented in this report. The full mapping table is available via the ENACT website [here](#). For detailed information regarding the SICUR exhibitors please refer to: <https://www.ifema.es/en/sicur/exhibitors/catalogue>

Exhibitors	Company self-description at SICUR website	URL
2N	2N, a technological leader in video intercom and access control.	https://www.2n.cz/en_GB/
4X4 PROMYGES	Experts in 4x4 vehicles	www.promyges4x4.com/
Abraresist, S.L.	We offer security solutions: anti-puncture systems, kits, and armored helmets. Working with a variety of products such as Air-Seal puncture sealant, International Runflat, Plates, and AAE armoured kits.	https://www.abreresist.net/
ABUS IBÉRICA	International leader in innovative security solutions with a wide product portfolio, ABUS IBÉRICA will have double participation in SICUR 2024. In Pavilion 10 dedicated to Security, they will show: the Bravus MX Pro Magnet Cylinder for doors that goes further in security with new Pro Cap wrench; Vitess MX, high security 3D curved profile serreta key system; and Vanlock, security lock for vans suitable for both rear and side doors. In Hall 4 dedicated to Occupational Safety, ABUS will present SMART LOTO ONE, its innovative system for consigning hazardous energy sources, both mechanical and digital. This system represents a significant advance in the comprehensive management of blocking and labelling of energy sources, as well as in the optimization of industrial safety processes and reduction of accident risks. In addition, it will present ABUS ONE, the new app for managing security cameras, lock operations, key storage and motorcycle-bicycle anti-theft devices.	https://www.abus.com/
AC iTEC	iTEC strives to be a globally recognized leader in quality and diversity of products and solutions in the access control field. With the dedication of the entire team, motivation, and passion, iTEC embraces best business practices.	https://itec-onaccess.com
ACCESOR	At Accesor, we specialize in access control systems for people and vehicles in all types of environments. We tailor security solutions, supply state-of-the-art equipment, and ensure seamless integration through quality service. Because in any space, safety comes first.	https://www.accesor.com/
ACTIVI SEGURIDAD Y SISTEMAS	Activi is a well-established company dedicated to distributing products for the electronic security market, including Fire Detection, CCTV, Intrusion, and Access Control, providing comprehensive solutions.	https://www.activi.es
AFORSEC	-	https://www.aforsec.com/
Ajax	Our mission is to combat evil by providing people with the best security and automation tools to overcome adversity. While protecting homes and businesses, we believe that safety should be accessible to all, and we are committed to making it a reality.	https://ajax.systems/
AKILA	Protective clothing.	https://www.akila.es/
ALARCLOUD	Spain's only manufacturer of intrusion systems (Alarms, Pir Cam, central magnetic contacts, power supplies among others), whose equipment is managed by clients from the cloud, through our cloud, and manipulated by end users through of our App. Alarcloud will show its technology at SICUR 2024 and present its added value.	https://www.alarcloud.com/

Exhibitors	Company self-description at SICUR website	URL
Alphanet Solutions	Alphanet, a leading company in municipal security solutions, with a strong track record of over 15 years in the field of video surveillance.	https://www.2n.cz/en_GB/
ALSICO	Alsico designs, produces, and provides high-quality workwear. This helps our clients focus on their core business, knowing that their workers are comfortable, safe, and have freedom of movement, even in the toughest work environments.	www.promyges4x4.com/
ALTER TECHNOLOGY	ALTER is a leading engineering company providing reliable, agile solutions for many of the world's most innovative technologies, including semiconductors, electronic equipment and geospatial intelligence.	https://www.abraresist.net/
AL-TOP TOPOGRAFIA S.A.	Official distributor of Trimble Forensics, providing precise 3D reconstruction solutions for crime scenes and traffic accidents. DJI Enterprise drones for fire monitoring and their use in public safety, rescues, and damage assessment.	https://www.abus.com/
AMC ELETTRONICA	AMC Elettronica is an entirely Italian-owned company founded in 1974. Our main activity is the production and marketing of components for alarm systems, including alarm panels, wireless devices, sensors, sirens, etc. AMC has an established international distribution network. It is known for excellent "made in Italy" products and pays special attention to detail in product design.	https://itec-onaccess.com
AQUALUNG MILITARY & PROFESSIONAL	The Military Professional Division of the Aqualung Group is exhibiting at Booth 10B09 Pavilion 10. We are showcasing our high-quality equipment and service solutions for emergency breathing, public safety divers, and rescue organizations.	https://www.accessor.com/
Arcano Equipos Especiales & ArcanoScan	Manufacturer of X-ray Inspection Equipment with automatic detection using Artificial Intelligence.	https://www.activi.es
ARCAS OLLE	Since 1845.	https://www.aforsec.com/
ARMATURA	ARMATURA was born with the aim of competing in a market of high-end solutions both in features and functionalities, as well as in compliance with the highest safety standards. For this reason, ZKTeco, a renowned global provider of security and access control solutions, has recently announced an exclusive global distribution agreement with ARMATURA.	https://ajax.systems/
ARREGUI	Innovative security solutions with the latest technology for connected security: Fingerprint safes, smart key management, door security and electronic locks.	https://www.akila.es/
A-SECUR	A-SECUR was founded more than 15 years ago as an approved installation company, subsequently modifying our activity to the distribution of security systems, knowing first-hand all the needs and concerns of installers. Our mission is to provide professional customer service with immediate attention, both at a commercial, technical and logistical level.	https://www.alarcloud.com/
ASSA ABLOY	ASSA ABLOY is the largest global provider of intelligent locking and security solutions. We attended SICUR 2024 with our TESA Security Center division, with the main novelty of Yale's new range of residential security products, among which the Yale Smart Video Doorbell stands out, as well as a new alarm and new cameras. In addition, we will show the TESA ASSA ABLOY header armoured doors: the Premium for replacement, the Cool pivoting door and the Bunker storage room door.	https://www.assaabloy.es/
Automatic Systems	With an outstanding track record in the development of advanced security systems, it presents FirstLane Plus, an innovative access control device that redefines efficiency and security standards for outdoors and outdoors and has recently been awarded as an outstanding perimeter security product. at the Intersec 2024 international fair in Dubai. In addition, the company hopes to share its knowledge and cutting-edge technologies with attendees, thus consolidating its position as a global leader in the access control and security sector.	https://www.automatic-systems.com/
Axon	-	https://www.axon.com

Exhibitors	Company self-description at SICUR website	URL
AYR OPENING DOORS	-	https://www.2n.cz/en_GB/
Bee the Data	-	https://www.beethedata.com/
BOSCH SECURITY AND SAFETY SYSTEMS	Nowadays, buildings not only provide a safe and functional place to live and work but can also meet and even respond to their needs, helping them work more efficiently and sustainably. The Internet of Things (IoT) and sensor-based technologies play a fundamental role in this regard.	https://www.abraresist.net/
BTV	-	https://www.abus.com/
Casmar	At Casmar, our mission is to offer comprehensive security solutions with added value. A differentiating factor that we have maintained with our clients, suppliers, market, and team for over four decades. We have a great team of professionals with the knowledge, experience, and professionalism to tackle any project and adapt to the necessary changes that allow us to continue growing alongside our clients.	https://www.casmarglobal.com/
CDVI - JIS	The CDVI Group is a global manufacturer of advanced security and access control solutions, offering a wide range of innovative products, from stand-alone and online access controls to next-generation door automation, biometrics and lock systems. CDVI manufactures high quality products that increase safety and improve mobility in any industrial, commercial or residential building.	https://cdviberica.com
CISA Cerraduras	CISA Cerraduras is a company founded in 1981, with its headquarters located in Calatayud (Zaragoza), where customer service, the commercial team, and logistics are based. It has two branches in Madrid and Barcelona, where commercial representatives and project prescription teams are located.	https://www.cisa.com/es/index.html
Concordia Textiles	Founded in 1925, Concordia Textiles has almost a century of experience in textile manufacturing and finishing. As a fully vertically integrated textile manufacturer, we control the entire production flow, from sizing and warping to weaving, dyeing, printing, finishing, coating and laminating fabrics. Concordia Textiles develops and produces textile solutions for selected professional markets. To ensure dedicated research and development along with high-quality service, our organization is divided into 4 Business Units: Workwear, Fashion, Bedding and Innovative Applications.	https://www.concordiatextiles.com/
CRISTANINI S.p.A	The Cristanini company, founded in 1972, has created a wide range of innovative solutions, appreciated around the world, in the civil/industrial and military fields. In addition, Cristanini is an international leader in the production of Water-Jetting equipment, and goes one step further in the creation of firefighting systems with advanced systems for the first attack on fire in open and confined areas. The effectiveness of these systems combines the success of Water Mist technology with low water and energy consumption. In addition, it provides solutions for decontamination and sanitation against the COVID-19 virus with the innovative VAPOR VACUUM M8 system.	https://www.cristanini.it
CSL Iberia	CSL has established itself as the leading European provider of Critical Connectivity and has become a benchmark in the communications industry. With over 25 years of experience in the sector, CSL has achieved an impressive milestone by managing more than 2.5 million active connections throughout Europe, providing robust support for essential applications used by sectors with Critical IoT Connectivity.	https://www.csl-group.es/
Cyber Human Systems	Cyber Human Systems is the only Spanish company where exoskeletons are designed and developed for the industry. As a spin-off of Gogo Mobility Robots, we are pioneers in the field of robotics and biomedical engineering. Over the past years, we have been involved in the development of advanced technology to create industrial exoskeletons that assist in various functions and sectors. Lightweight assistance devices help workers enhance their human capabilities, reduce sick leave, and prevent musculoskeletal disorders.	https://www.cyberhs.eu/

Exhibitors	Company self-description at SICUR website	URL
Dahua Technology	Experts in intrusion detection. For over 15 years, we have been exclusively dedicated to research and development of video analysis for perimeter security. Our dedication and experience have made us experts in solutions with proprietary technology compatible with all security systems in the market.	https://www.dahuasecurity.com/
DAITEM ESPAÑA	DAITEM is a manufacturer of radio video intrusion systems with special patented "TWINBAND" anti-jamming technology. It offers reliability, long range, simplicity, technical assistance, only distributed by security professionals.	https://www.daitem.es/
DAVANTIS	Experts in intrusion detection. For over 15 years, we have been exclusively dedicated to research and development of video analysis for perimeter security. Our dedication and experience have made us experts in solutions with proprietary technology compatible with all security systems in the market.	https://www.davantis.com/
DIMATEX	Created in 1996 and based near Lyon (Rhône Alps - France) on a key crossroad location, DIMATEX is a medium-sized company specialized in technical textiles. We develop, produce and commercialize textile equipment (cases, covers, bags, rescue belts, fall protection belts, etc.) suited for professionals of various sectors of activity such as airline, medical, defence or rescue. The company has its own engineering, sampling, textile confection and after sales services. Its size allows one-off as well as large productions for defence and industry markets for examples. Our in-house storage platform and our logistic organization allow us to offer flexible and responsive delivery conditions: immediate, periodic, cyclical and dispatched deliveries.	https://www.dimatex.fr
DOM-MCM	Individual protection equipment.	https://www.dom-security.com/es/es
DORCAS	Dorcás is an international leader in electromechanical/electromagnetic opening and closing systems. being present in more than 73 countries and with a product range that includes: door openers, electromechanical locks, electromagnetic locks, magnetic retainers, access control, pushbuttons and power supplies, cable glands, door closers and door automation and other accessories.	https://www.dorcás.com/
DORLET	DORLET, with more than 35 years of experience in the sector, has stood out as a leader in the protection of Critical Infrastructures through its own Comprehensive Security Systems solutions. During this time, it has demonstrated its ability to adapt to the constant changes that characterize access and security systems. One of DORLET's strengths lies in its customer-centric approach, which is reflected in the ability to provide tailored solutions that meet the specific needs of each client. This customization extends to its high level of integration with third-party security systems, enabling seamless interoperability and greater security management effectiveness.	https://www.dorlet.com/
DRAG	DRAG is a computer program for the management of police forces and municipal surveillance. It is a web application that does not require any installation on the computer and at the same time can also operate through mobile devices (Android, IOS, or Windows phones and tablets) through our Apps. Agents, in addition to being able to enter services from the same application and incorporate photographs of incidents or violations from the scene, can also consult their work calendar, request shift changes, licenses or consult their court summons.	https://www.drag.es/
Eagle Eye networks	Eagle Eye Networks is the global leader in cloud video surveillance, delivering cyber-secure, cloud-based video with artificial intelligence (AI) and analytics to make businesses more efficient and the world a safer place. Eagle Eye provides security and real-time business intelligence, helping organizations of all sizes and types optimize operations.	https://www.een.com/

Exhibitors	Company self-description at SICUR website	URL
EcaptureDtech	The only platform that allows you to generate, import and export 3D models, as well as interact with them with more than 60 tools. It allows the generation of three-dimensional models of objects, environments and people, from images (videos or photographs) taken with any device that has a camera. Carrying out this process in just three simple steps: capture, upload and view.	https://www.ecapturedtech.com/
EUROMA TELECOM	Since 1993, Euroma has integrated a group of R&D professionals with extensive experience in the field of telecommunications. Our activity focuses on the distribution and development of products for the Security world. Euroma offers a portfolio of solutions in AI, Video, Intrusion, and Access Control with the latest technological advances, thanks to collaboration with our international partners. Internationally renowned companies such as Pelco, Kedacom, Eldes, IronYun, Crow, KT&C, or Anviz have entrusted us with the distribution of their solutions.	https://www.ferrimax.com/
EZVIZ IBERIA	-	https://www.ezviz.com/es/
FERRIMAX	With over 45 years of experience in the sector, Ferrimax positions itself at the forefront of technological advances in the field of physical security, addressing the most demanding market needs.	https://www.ferrimax.com/
FM Approvals	-	https://www.fmapprovals.com/
Genetec	Genetec Inc. is a global technology company that has been transforming the electronic security industry for over 25 years. It also develops cloud-based solutions and services designed to enhance security and provide new levels of operational intelligence for governments, businesses, transportation, and the communities in which we live. The company's flagship product, Security Center, is an open-architecture platform that unifies video surveillance, access control, license plate recognition (LPR), communications, and video analytics, all based on IP networks. Founded in 1997 and headquartered in Montreal, Canada, Genetec serves its customers worldwide through an extensive network of distributors, integrators, and business partners.	https://www.genetec.com/
GETAC	Getac Technology Corporation es líder mundial en tecnología móvil ruggedizada y soluciones de video inteligentes, que incluyen ordenadores portátiles, tablets, software, cámaras corporales, sistemas de vídeo en vehículos, accesorios y servicios profesionales.	https://www.getac.com/
GLOBAL PROOF S.r.l.	-	https://www.globalproof.it/
GORE-TEX PROFESSIONAL	-	https://www.gore-tex.com/professional
GRUPO ESTUDIOS TECNICOS	GET is an international organization that develops consulting projects in Intelligence and Global Security through highly qualified professionals, with extensive experience in Comprehensive Risk Management, Intelligence, Research and Knowledge Management.	http://www.getseguridad.com
GUARDIAN	Representante oficial en España de los principales fabricantes israelíes de material policial y militar.	https://www.guardianspain.com/
GUARNICIONERIA ROAL, S.A.	Three generations since Guarnicionería Roal, S.A. began making military harnesses in 1900. From the first workshop located in the heart of old Madrid to the modern current factory in Pinto, many satisfied customers have used products from Guarnicionería Roal, S.A. across five continents. In recent years, international presence at fairs, exhibitions, and trade missions has contributed to its continued growth.	https://roal.com/guarnicioneria
IBD Global	IBD Global is the leading company in innovative security solutions specializing in video, access control, intrusion, and fire.	https://www.ibdglobal.com/

Exhibitors	Company self-description at SICUR website	URL
IBS Iberia	IBS IBERIA is presenting a revolutionary service worldwide in the industry: Monitoring On Cloud. This service allows Alarm Reception (ARC) companies to start their operations quickly, without the need for physical receivers in their facilities. It includes mobility applications (Acudas, Técnicos, User, Safe & Secure and WithU) to increase the productivity and efficiency of the ARC, as well as the integration of video with video analysis. In addition, we offer alarm treatment through the web with SBN Anywhere, promoting greater mobility for CRAs. We also introduce new web management models for the entire system cycle, from pre-sales to technical and recurring security services. We invite you to learn about these news during the event and we hope to have your presence.	https://www.ibsiberia.com/
Ifam Seguridad S.L.U	-	https://www.ifam.es/
iLOQ	Digital locks.	https://www.iloq.com/
INSTANT BYTE	Instant Byte, a specialized wholesaler in networking, voice, security solutions, and IoT, and a pioneer in wireless networks, is one of the leading companies in the sector in Spain and Portugal.	https://www.instantbyte.com/
INTERSAFE	Experts in occupational safety and PPE (Personal Protective Equipment).	https://www.intersafe.eu/
ITURRI	ITURRI is a family group with origins in Seville (Spain) founded in 1947 dedicated to the manufacture of garments, equipment and vehicles for Industrial Security and Protection, Emergencies, Defence and Health.	https://www.iturri.com/
Johnson Controls	-	https://www.johnsoncontrols.com/
KENWOOD	Specialist in Car Electronics and Professional Communications products.	https://www.kenwood.com/
Kimaldi - Suprema - Evolis	Kimaldi, with its usual focus on innovation and cutting-edge technology, will showcase the latest solutions in access control, time and attendance, and card printers, in collaboration with its prestigious partner brands, Suprema and Evolis.	https://www.kimaldi.com/
Komunica Power Accessories S.L.	Komunica Power, a Spanish company specialized in the development and distribution of high-quality audio accessories and antennas for professional radiocommunication, with its own brands Komunica® and Komunica PWR®.	https://www.komunica.es/
Ksenia Security S.p.A.	Ksenia Security is an Italian company that designs and produces innovative solutions in the field of security, video verification, access control, and smart homes. It was founded in 2010 thanks to the vision of its founders, who firmly believed in surprising the security market with exceptionally innovative and reliable solutions. The company has grown significantly over the years: we have built a new state-of-the-art headquarters, expanded our global presence, and launched numerous products and features. We actively collaborate with distributors, installers, and systems integrators to continuously exchange ideas and listen, creating solutions that perfectly meet market needs. Ksenia Security is a strong and competent team, always ready to face new challenges with enthusiasm and determination.	https://www.kseniasecurity.com/
Lanaccess	Lanaccess is a Spanish multinational with over 25 years of experience in research, development, and manufacturing of video surveillance solutions.	https://www.lanaccess.com/
Lenard BCN, S.L.	At Lenard, we develop technical fabrics for various sectors of activity and innovate in the search for new fabrics that enhance labour protection. Since 1996, we have worked to combine experience, knowledge, and a willingness to innovate, becoming a reference company in the occupational safety sector. We offer solutions for each sector that protect against hazards such as electric arcs, heat, sparks, or metal splashes, while ensuring proper visibility for workers in low-light conditions. Our wide range of fabrics provides workplace protection for different sectors of activity, meeting the requirements established by international certifications.	https://www.lenardbcn.com/

Exhibitors	Company self-description at SICUR website	URL
M2M Services	M2M Services is on a mission to accelerate mass adoption of smart security around the world through universal and affordable IoT solutions. The company creates simple, innovative and reliable technology that helps alarm companies bring smart security to every home and business in the world.	https://www.m2mservices.com
MISSION TRACK	Mission Track is a technology-based company specialized in emergency management software solutions. This innovative mobile technology-based app allows for the digitization of deployment, command, and real-time control processes for intervention teams in emergency management. It has revolutionized management and coordination, making it faster, safer, and more effective. It is already successfully operating in industrial companies across various sectors.	https://www.missiontrack.es/
Motorola Solutions	Motorola Solutions.	https://www.motorolasolutions.com/
MundiCam Security Distribution	MundiCam Security Distribution is a global provider of security systems for professionals, installers and businesses. It distributes a complete portfolio of solutions, such as IP security cameras, CCTV, anti-intrusion systems, access control, fire alarms, drones, autonomous protection and security systems, among others.	https://www.mundicam.com/
NELS Work Safety	We are a multinational leader in Spain dedicated to the design, manufacture, and marketing of PPE (Personal Protective Equipment), accessories, and individual protection complements. We have over 25 years of experience in tailoring technical clothing for various professional sectors. We prioritize innovation in our products, the quality of our finishes, and sustainability in our production processes. Under our production process “We create with you,” we ensure that the PPE and other products we market meet the requirements and needs of our customers.	https://www.nelsworksafety.com/
Network Optix	Network Optix (Nx) is a powerhouse in video software development, driven by a mission to empower the creation of intelligent video-based solutions and products capable of converting video into actionable data.	https://www.networkoptix.com/
NIDEC DEFENSE GROUP	-	https://www.nidec.es/
Openers & Closers	Openers & Closers is a leading company in designing and manufacturing access control systems, specializing in mechanical, electromechanical, electromagnetic, and electronic solutions.	https://www.openers-closers.com/
OPTEX	OPTEX is the leading manufacturer of detection systems. The OPTEX Group, founded in 1979 in Japan, is a global solutions provider that continuously innovates to create a safe, protected, and comfortable society.	https://www.optexamerica.com/
ORCROM SEGURIDAD	At Orcrom Seguridad, we are specialists in providing security solutions to guarantee the protection and access control of people and packages in critical environments. Our VMI® brand X-ray Inspection Equipment and GARRETT® brand metal detectors are recognized worldwide for their high precision, efficiency and reliability.	https://www.orcrom.com/
PUERTAS CABMA	Design, manufacture, and sale of security armored doors.	https://www.puertascabma.com/
QUALICA-RD Sistemas de Identificación Automática	Qualica-RD is a company specialized in automatic identification systems, access control, and advanced technology. It has continued to grow since its foundation in 20122.	https://qualicard.eu/
Reconeyez	Innovation Leader in Professional Alarm System now Available in Spain.	https://www.reconeyez.com/

Exhibitors	Company self-description at SICUR website	URL
RISCO Group	Developing cloud-based security solutions, along with video verification, monitoring and automation, RISCO Group offers innovative, high-quality and reliable security systems for every type of security installation for the residential and commercial markets.	https://www.riscogroup.com/m
RISTER	At SICUR it will show the latest developments in CCTV systems from the different brands it sells, among which AVIGILON stands out, with its system based on Artificial Intelligence and state-of-the-art video analytics, as well as IP cameras with resolutions of up to 30 megapixels. They will also have their flagship brand PRESENTCO, which has accompanied them during these 40 years of experience in the sector, as well as traffic solutions, our new cloud-based LPR CLOUD. And on-board CCTV systems from the manufacturer VIVOTEK.	https://www.rister.com/
Salto Systems	SCATI is a manufacturer of intelligent video surveillance systems, with open, cybersecure solutions tailored to your needs.	https://www.saltosystems.com/
SCATI	MundiCam Security Distribution is a global provider of security systems for professionals, installers and businesses. It distributes a complete portfolio of solutions, such as IP security cameras, CCTV, anti-intrusion systems, access control, fire alarms, drones, autonomous protection and security systems, among others.	https://www.scati.com/
SECUREMME SRL - Security Locks - Made in Italy	Securemme, by your side in security since 1967.	https://securemme.it/
SECURimport	SECURimport Technology S.L. is an international distributor of electronic security systems, specializing in CCTV, intrusion, fire detection, access control, and video analytics.	https://www.securimport.com/
Senstar	With intelligent video management, video analytics, access control, and innovative perimeter intrusion detection systems, Senstar offers a comprehensive suite of proven, integrated technologies that reduce complexity, improve performance, and unify support.	https://www.senstar.com/
SISTELEC	Sistelec, a company with more than 40 years of experience in the critical communications market, offers its clients a large portfolio of technological solutions and services focused on worker safety, whether in an industrial or business environment, as well as in bodies. specific to emergencies such as firefighters, police, health, forestry, etc.	https://www.sistelec.es/
SLRescue - SERVICIOS Y LOGISTICA DE RESCATE SL	SLRescue operates in various fields, which enables us to have expertise in a wide range of solutions and products tailored to specific needs.	https://www.slrescue.com/
SoftGuard Ibérica	Softguard Tech Ibérica is an organization made up of professionals with extensive experience in IT and Information Systems and Security. Established in 2011, our mission is to serve our clients by developing and implementing IT and security systems, distributing, marketing, and maintaining hardware, software, and information security products.	https://www.softguard.com/
SoSafe	SoSafe permite a las organizaciones crear una cultura de ciberseguridad y convertir a sus empleados en sus mejores defensas contra las amenazas digitales. La plataforma de concienciación de SoSafe está basada en la ciencia del comportamiento, utiliza algoritmos inteligentes y, además, es fácil de implementar, escalable y divertida de usar. Somos el principal proveedor europeo de concienciación y formación en ciberseguridad y la empresa de concienciación sobre ciberseguridad de más rápido crecimiento en todo el mundo. Ponemos nuestro foco en las personas y nos basamos en la ciencia del comportamiento, lo que nos permite cambiar el statu quo de la concienciación sobre ciberseguridad.	https://www.sosafe.net/

Exhibitors	Company self-description at SICUR website	URL
Squire Locks	As a family-owned business founded in 1780, we are immensely proud of our craftsmanship and wholeheartedly uphold our reputation for durability and longevity. As a testament to our commitment, we provide a personal 10-year warranty on all our products.	https://www.squirelocks.co
STAR ROBOTICS	Star Robotics is a Robot company, founded by Angel Andrade Gómez, focused on the development and commercialization of terrestrial robotic platforms with autonomous navigation and artificial intelligence capabilities.	https://www.rister.com/
Synguard	Synguard is the future of access management with an innovative, secure, and flexible platform. Their cutting-edge solutions seamlessly bridge the gap between physical security and evolving business needs.	https://www.synguard.be
SYX image wear and safety garments	After 10 years in the design and production of fashion clothing for the European market, we founded SYX Co., Ltd in 2015 with a focus on safety and standardized garments (PPE).	-
Target Tecnología	-	https://www.target-tecnologia.es/
Technicaluniforms	A textile company specialized in manufacturing various technical garments for law enforcement, firefighters, and emergency services.	https://www.technicaluniforms.com/
TECNITRÁN TELECOMUNICACIONES	Tecnitrán is a company with over 30 years of experience in the telecommunications sector, providing comprehensive solutions tailored to each company's needs. Their areas of activity include professional walkie talkies, video surveillance, unified communications, headphones, access control, and walkie rental. They are technology partners with leading manufacturers such as Motorola Solutions, Avigilon, Kenwood, Jabra, Poly, and ZKTeco, among others.	https://www.tecnitran.es/
TEDEE	Tedee, de origen polaco, es el fabricante de la cerradura inteligente más compacta y resistente de Europa. La misión de la compañía es "poner una cerradura inteligente en cada puerta" con el objetivo de hacernos la vida más fácil y cómoda. El equipo de Tedee cuenta con una amplia experiencia en el desarrollo de software aplicado al diseño y la fabricación de productos de seguridad inteligente, incluido su último lanzamiento: Tedee Go, una cerradura inteligente excepcionalmente segura y elegante. El equipo se complementa con expertos en hardware, gestión comercial, gestión logística, marketing y atención al cliente. Todos ellos están comprometidos a garantizar una experiencia de cliente fluida y agradable.	https://www.tedee.com/
TELECTRISA	Wholesale distributor of electronic security products (burglar alarms, fire and gas alarms, closed circuit television, access control) and video intercoms, as well as their accessories (batteries, special cables, etc.)	https://www.telectrisa.com/
Textil-r	At Grupo Textil-r, we specialize in uniforms, professional attire, workwear, and technical clothing for all sectors and work environments. With over two decades of commitment to enhancing your company's image, we offer expertise, creativity, and high-quality professional workwear.	https://www.textil-r.com/
TP-Link	TP-Link, a leading provider of consumer and business networking products, has been consistently ranked as the No. 1 global provider of WLAN devices for 10 years, according to the IDC Quarterly Wireless LAN Tracker, Q4 2020.	https://www.tp-link.com/
TRADESEGUR	Comprehensive solutions in Mobility and Citizen Security. Long business trajectory. Solid business group present in complementary sectors. Great adaptability to the environment and the customer.	https://www.tradesegur.com/
Veridas	Veridas is a technology company that offers solutions to verify the real identity of people in the digital and physical space. We do this by developing proprietary technologies for facial biometrics, voice biometrics, and identity document verification, and AI-powered IoT devices.	https://www.veridas.com/
Verifait-Vaelsys	-	https://verifaisys.com/

Exhibitors	Company self-description at SICUR website	URL
VISIOTECH	Visiotech is a company mainly dedicated to the import and distribution of video surveillance equipment and security systems; a leader in the Spanish market with a strong international presence.	https://www.visiotechsecurity.com/
XXII	Our revolutionary technology extracts essential data from your video streams, providing in-depth understanding that can transform your operations. Whether you're seeking enhanced security or operational excellence in key sectors like retail, quick restaurant service, logistics, smart cities, or public infrastructure, XXII has the solution. Our expertise in capturing and analysing video streams opens up new possibilities to streamline your processes, increase efficiency, and ensure remarkable outcomes.	https://www.xxii.com/
Zenitel COITEL	Zenitel es un proveedor mundial líder de Soluciones Inteligentes de Comunicación Crítica. Nuestra misión es mantener la seguridad de las personas haciendo posible que todas las personas puedan oír, ser oídas y ser entendidas, en todo momento y en todo lugar. Nuestra principal oferta de sistemas abarca Interfonía, Megafonía, Alarma por voz y Altavoces IP. Con nuestra marca Zenitel, somos reconocidos mundialmente por ofrecer sistemas de comunicación avanzados y fiables. Nuestra gama incluye productos basados en nuestras tecnologías Vingtor, Stentofon, Phontech y ASL.	https://www.zenitel.com/

APPENDIX B - SICUR CONFERENCES

The following table shows the SICUR conferences that are relevant to the FCT domain and which have been used in the analysis presented in this report. The full mapping table is available via the ENACT website [here](#). For detailed information regarding the SICUR conferences please refer to: <https://www.ifema.es/sicur/horario-actividades>

Conference title
IBV - Exoskeleton
AI in the Fight Against Domestic Violence: A Police Perspective
Biosafety - Hand Exoskeleton
Innovation and Public Funding for IT Projects
Regulatory Horizon: NIS 2 and CER Transpositions
The Role of Security in Cultural Heritage Management
Healthy Suits
Ergo-Santé Exoskeleton - AI
Cyber Manipulation: How Can We Combat Brain Hacking?
Panter - AI in Footwear
Cybersecurity in a Connected World
Basic Passive Protection Product Sheets
Cyber Human Systems
Fit Testing in Respiratory Protection
Cybersecurity for Security: Finally Underway
43 Years of AES Energizing the Private Security Industry
Cybersecurity in the Lifecycle of Security Devices
Presentation of the 2024 PPE Selection Guide
National Cybersecurity Forum: Guide for Cyber-Secure Physical Security
Recommendations for a Cyber-Secure Physical Security Solution
Presentation of the III Women and Security Study
Certification of Security Engineers in Cybersecurity
Strategies for Cybercrime by Security Forces and Bodies
CEUSS - Security Cameras - AI
Social Engineering and Physical Security
Biometric Data Treatment for Security Purposes
Training and Development Paths in Cybersecurity
UDRUME, the Drone Unit of the Military Emergency Unit

APPENDIX C - SICUR INNOVATION GALLERY PRODUCTS

The following table shows the products exhibited at the SICUR innovation gallery that are relevant to the FCT domain and which have been used in the analysis presented in this report. The full mapping table is available via the ENACT website [here](#). For detailed information regarding the SICUR innovation gallery please refer to <https://www.ifema.es/sicur/galeria-innovacion>

Conference title	Product name	Description
Arcano Equipos Especiales S.L. Stand: 10F11	Artificial Intelligence for the detection of 70 dangerous items in X-ray scanners of any Brand or model	Through artificial intelligence and its learning algorithm, prohibited items are intelligently identified in X-ray images. Among them are knives, guns, bottles, spray cans, scissors, lighters, bullets, fireworks, tools, batteries, mobile phones, and medication pills.
Bosch Service Solutions S.A.U. Stand: 10E15	Dinion 7100i IR	A range of bullet cameras specialized in reliable detection and precise classification for perimeter surveillance and traffic monitoring. The new camera portfolio offers exceptional accuracy, reliable long-range detection, precise classification, outstanding low-light performance, and valuable information.
Bosch Service Solutions S.A.U. Stand: 10E15	Autodome 7100i IR	A range of intelligent cameras with deep learning video analysis that enhance urban surveillance, traffic control, and long-distance perimeter detection. Cutting-edge artificial intelligence with ultra-simplified installation and no calibration required.
Commend Ibérica S.L. Stand: 10I26	Ivy, el Asistente Virtual para Interfonía	This conversational voice assistant for intercoms is based on artificial intelligence. It can interpret and respond to open-ended questions using natural language understanding. Developed following the principles of "Privacy and Security by Design," Ivy ensures it always functions when needed, with all data handled securely.
Optex. Stand: 10G16	Optex Redscan mini-Pro	Combines the precision of 2D LiDAR technology with the capabilities of an advanced surveillance camera. It provides highly accurate intrusion detection and visual verification for a wide range of applications. Extremely reliable and versatile, it creates high-resolution virtual laser walls or planes with a detection range of 20x20 meters. The sensor delivers ultra-fast detection and analyzes the size, location, and distance of a moving object to determine an intrusion. It features an integrated camera that allows real-time verification of alarm causes while recording and storing video sequences and detailed logs for later analysis.
Risco Group Iberia S.L. Stand: 10E16	RisControl	This controller is an 8-inch touchscreen keypad that incorporates alarm, video surveillance (cameras and NVR), and Z-Wave Smart Home devices into an easy-to-use interface. It provides an exceptional user experience, ease of use, and a fully customizable interface. It is a professional home security and automation solution that utilizes an integrated Smart Home controller with Risco's hybrid alarm system.
Saborit International S.L. Stand: 10E06	goTenna Pro X2	This small, lightweight, cost-effective mesh network device is designed for tactical operations. Used as an independent repeater or paired with a mobile phone, the goTenna Pro X2 network provides critical situational awareness for missions, both in the air and on the ground, for deployment and tactical movement.

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